

ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE PERFORMANCE OF CARS IN THE HOT CLIMATE OF URBAN CITY

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Abstract: *This article presents measures to address the challenges of implementing techniques and technologies that can be introduced in order to develop the rapid, convenient and systematic movement of cars in urban and rural areas in hot climates of the Republic. An analysis of the implementation of targeted work on implementation has been conducted.*

Keywords: *power, permeability, road conditions, energy source, road categories, traffic, road zone, performance characteristics, operational characteristics of cars.*

Introduction. To date, a comprehensive work plan in various areas and directions is being implemented in the country. Representatives of each field make a significant contribution to the development of society through their scientific research. We all know that today's demand is a society based on technology and technology, in which the individual has the right to take advantage of the evolving opportunities. As our times progress, we can see a strategy of continuous growth in all areas. However, such growth is accompanied by the development of our country on a global scale.

One example is the automotive industry. We know that it has been serving our people through a long-term, time-efficient source, an aesthetic pleasure, a heavy-duty feature, in terms of productivity, and a number of positive qualities. Of course, without neglecting one thing, we can say that the efficiency, speed, quality of work of different

types of cars depends on one factor, which is the quality of roads in motion. What does it mean? We know we still have a lot to be happy about, but we also need to keep in mind that we have roadmaps that we can't even begin to describe. To put it bluntly, the highest value is a human being. So what do you think the human and automotive industries have to do with each other? We have mentioned above why it is necessary for human needs. Imagine! Can you organize your business one day without using cars? No. Do you know why? Because one of the most desirable features of cars is the long-distance approach. Based on the above considerations, our main goal is to qualitatively and systematically regulate the movement of cars in hot urban conditions, to analyze the problems that may be encountered and, if necessary, to develop new types of equipment and facilities.

Research results. The scientific and practical significance of the research is that we believe that the reasons for the chaotic movement of cars in hot climates are:

- road conditions;
- transport conditions;
- natural climatic conditions.

From the above, it can be seen that 3 main factors are the revolutionary reason for the systematic movement of cars.

Road conditions - longitudinal and transverse elements of the road; topography; type and flatness of the road surface; movement intensity; obstacles to movement; uniformity of road conditions; movement mode. Road conditions affect the operation of the unit and parts, the rate of change of technical parameters can be accelerated or slowed down. They determine the operating mode of the vehicle, which affects reliability. Road conditions are determined by the technical category of the road, the type and quality of the road surface, the resistance to traffic, the width of the road, the radii of turns, elevations and slopes.

Transport conditions - type of cargo; carrying capacity; shipping method; transportation distance; loading and unloading method; operating mode; types of transportation organization and route; cargo storage conditions; conditions of maintenance and repair of cars. Transport conditions ensure the specialization of the rolling stock, which corresponds to the process of transportation for a particular load.

Natural climatic conditions - temperate, cold, hot and high mountain climates. Natural climatic conditions are determined by air temperature, atmospheric pressure, wind strength and direction, and types of precipitation. These conditions affect the thermal and other operating modes of the units and, consequently, their technical condition and reliability. Under the influence of low and high temperatures, the physical and mechanical properties of structural steels, metal alloys, plastics, rubber and other materials change. Physicochemical constants of oils, fuels, brake and shock absorbers, electrolytes, etc. change under the influence of climatic conditions.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Motor Roads” of June 29, 2007 provides for a number of systematic measures for the effective introduction of highways. The force of impact between the tires and the road is very important. The two must be compatible. It is advisable to first analyze the components of the roads, and then develop a new type of technology for this road. Significantly, it needs to be developed from a regional perspective.

Figure 1. Pictures of tire tread.

As you can see from the picture above, each tire is adapted to move in different road environments.

Performance indicators

The ability of a car to move continuously in difficult road conditions and off-road terrain, overcoming various obstacles, is called the property of permeability. The ability of a car to pass through roadblocks depends mainly on the task it performs and the operating conditions. For example, there are no high traffic requirements for passenger cars traveling on high-class roads within the city and between cities. However, one of the main problems is to ensure the passage of road barriers for all types of vehicles intended for use on roads with different pavements in the field. In particular, high

permeability requirements are set for trucks used in agriculture, construction, mining and military purposes. When the car is moving in difficult road conditions, its permeability is affected by several road factors, including: 1) a decrease in the coefficient of adhesion between the wheels and the road; 2) deformation of the soil on soft paved roads due to the load on the car wheels; 3) natural and artificial barriers (thick snow, soil piles, rocks, tree trunks, thick bushes, ditches and pipes, etc.); 4) barriers consisting of water and swamps; 5) Slopes and slopes of the first road. Permeability is divided into two types: 1) profile, ie geometric permeability; 2) basic permeability. Profile permeability is determined by the geometric dimensions of the car and is assessed by the following parameters (Figure 2).

Unusual problems on the roads and in dry climates cannot be ignored. As we can see, the deformation of the asphalt on the roads in hot weather, the corrosion of the outer tires observed in cars, is one of the reasons we need to think about. For these reasons, the goal we are trying to achieve is somewhat backward. What to do for this? It is necessary to pay attention to the addition of additional ingredients to the asphalt-concrete composition and to the correct choice of ingredients. The goal can be achieved by adding a number of ways, such as density, composition, and methods of deposition. Natural asphalt is formed from heavy parts of oil or their residues, by evaporation of its light components and oxidation by hypergenesis. As a result of the analysis and research, we can say that the asphalt content of asphalt concrete is 60-75%. If this value is tested in two ways, the goal can be achieved by increasing or decreasing the amount by 10%.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that it is possible to introduce high-quality traffic, to establish a system of bilateral relations, to implement innovations, taking into account the balance of materials and equipment. As a result of the analysis, we learned that the result can

be achieved by changing the asphalt-concrete composition in order to create a favorable environment for roads and cars.

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